

Creative Approaches for Drug Education: Public Elementary School Teachers in Focus

Josephine R. Cubol

Abstract. The study explored the challenges of public school elementary teachers in employing creative approaches in drug education. The study employed a phenomenological research design which aimed to determine the experiences and perceptions of the eight (8) participants. The findings revealed emerging themes regarding teachers' challenges: superficial learning and potential misinterpretation. In contrast, the positive effects of encountering these challenges included increased student self-confidence and improved communication and presentation skills. Emerging themes in teachers' coping strategies included designing purposeful activities, clearing learning objectives, personalizing learning, and aligning with evidence-based information. Educational management insights gained from their experiences were responsible decision-making, proficiency in connecting ideas, and expression of individuality. The themes suggested that creative teaching imparts factual knowledge while fostering critical thinking, empathy, and personal responsibility. It empowers informed decisions about drug use and promotes understanding and open communication. These research findings suggested that public elementary school teachers were significant in fostering a holistic approach to drug education. This was essential for developing a comprehensive drug education curriculum where learners were empowered and engaged in their learning experiences.

KEY WORDS

1. creative teaching approaches 2. teachers 3. drug education

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1. Introduction

In today's complex and interconnected world, the health and well-being of our society's future lie in the hands of the youngest generation. As a critical phase in a child's development, elementary school teachers act as facilitators, imparting crucial life skills, values, and knowledge. Among the paramount concerns for teachers is the issue of drug abuse prevention. Substance abuse poses severe risks to young minds and can impede their physical, cognitive, emotional, and social growth. Consequently, the implementation of comprehensive drug education in elementary schools has gained recognition as a vital strategy in cultivating a drug-free and resilient generation. In addition, in the realm of elementary school drug education, the incorporation of creative teaching approaches by the teachers has emerged as an innovative strategy to engage young learners and impart vital knowledge effectively (Bekkering, 2018). These creative methods, such as role-playing, storytelling, art projects, music, and interactive

games, promise to cultivate informed decision-making and empower learners to make healthy choices throughout their lives (Faggiano, 2018). According to Hopfer's (2018) research conducted in Brazilian elementary schools, teachers' creative teaching approaches, such as interactive games, role-playing, and art projects, effectively engage learners, making the learning experience enjoyable. Additionally, Jackson et al. (2019) found that when drug education is delivered creatively and engagingly by teachers, learners develop positive attitudes towards the subject. Teachers help elementary school learners perceive drug education as relevant and valuable instead of seeing it as a tedious or uninteresting topic. Moreover, in the sphere of drug education implementation in elementary schools in Thailand, researchers like Nation (2018) observed that teachers help learners retain the knowledge and skills acquired over an extended period of time when they expose them to creative teaching approaches. The lasting impact of their strategy equips learners to make informed decisions beyond their elementary school years. Likewise, Madruga et al. (2018) found that creative approaches of teachers stimulate elementary school learners to analyze and assess situations concerning drug use. Through activities like role-playing and discussions, learners develop critical thinking abilities, empowering them to make informed choices and effectively resist peer pressure. On the other hand, according to studies conducted in the Philippines, including Rowando (2020), it was revealed that creative teaching methods of Filipino teachers frequently incorporate hands-on activities and experiential learning, which have demonstrated positive effects on improving knowledge and awareness among elementary school learners. Additionally, Sanchez (2019) highlighted that storytelling and interactive activities in drug education often prompt elementary school learners to empathize with characters who have experienced the effects of drug abuse. Through these activities, teachers foster empathy and compassion in learners, motivating them to support and understand those individuals facing challenges with substance use. In the study's setting, the Laak North District, Davao de Oro, elementary school teachers confirmed their active engagement in training and support to effectively utilize creative teaching approaches. They reported attending professional development opportunities that equipped them with the necessary skills and confidence to implement these methods in drug education successfully. Additionally, they observed that implementing these creative teaching strategies resulted in elementary school learners being actively engaged and more interested in drug education lessons than when these strategies were not used. It was evident that existing literature on drug education has extensively explored the benefits and advantages of creative teaching approaches to elementary school learners. These studies have shown that these methods effectively engage learners and enhance their interest and participation in drug education lessons. However, there was a noticeable gap in research focusing on teachers' experiences when employing innovative teaching methods, encompassing lesson planning, acquiring learning materials, and implementation. Therefore, this study concentrated on addressing this gap. Also, although many studies have underscored the beneficial effects of creative teaching techniques on learners' lives, there has been insufficient focus on exploring how teachers' experiences, encompassing their difficulties and strategies for overcoming them, with these methods might impact learners' educational achievements. Teachers play a crucial role in implementing creative teaching strategies and shaping the classroom environment, and their experiences and perspectives can significantly impact learners' learning experiences. Overall, this study's results assist educators, policymakers, and curriculum developers in enhancing the utilization of creative

methods, resulting in more effective and influential drug education programs. Furthermore, the study's findings promote healthy social behaviors by enabling individuals to acquire valuable insights into fostering open communication, empathy, and understanding regarding the sensitive topic of illegal drugs, aligning closely with the objectives of creative teaching methods.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to explore the experiences of public elementary school teachers in employing creative approaches in drug education. By examining these experiences, the study identified the challenges teachers face and their best coping practices—educational insights from their experiences open avenues for improving drug education in public elementary schools. In addition, the findings contribute to developing evidence-based, learner-centered drug education programs and highlight positive social behaviors such as open communication, empathy, and understanding, promoting an active and receptive approach to drug education.

1.2. Research Questions—The primary research questions of this study were the following:

- (1) What are the challenges of teachers in employing creative approaches in drug education for public school teachers?
- (2) How do teachers cope with the challenges of employing creative approaches in drug education for elementary school teachers?
- (3) What educational insights can be drawn from the experiences of the teachers in employing creative approaches in drug education?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following were the terms used in the study: Creative teaching strategies. These were innovative and imaginative approaches teachers used to engage students and enhance the learning experience. These strategies go beyond traditional methods of instruction and involve using various techniques, activities, and materials to stimulate students' curiosity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. Drug education. It was the process of providing individuals, typically learners or young people, with knowledge and information about drugs, their effects, risks, and consequences. The primary goal of drug education is to promote awareness and understanding of the potential harms associated with drug use. Elementary. In the context of the Philippine education system and the K to 12 Curriculum, "elementary" refers to the first six years of basic education provided to children, typically aged 6 to 11.

1.4. Significant of the Study—This study holds significant implications for multiple stakeholders in the field of education, including policymakers, school principals, teachers, and students: Policy Makers. This study's findings informed the development of drug education curricula that incorporate creative teaching approaches. By understanding the challenges and successes faced by teachers, policymakers can ensure that the curriculum aligns with their needs and capabilities, making it more likely to be effectively implemented in elementary schools. School Administrators. The findings of this study guided the enhancement of teacher training programs in their respective schools, providing teachers with the necessary support and skills to utilize creative methods in drug education effectively. School administrators can design professional development opportunities that address teachers' specific challenges,

thus increasing their confidence and competence in using creative approaches. Teachers. The study's findings informed them of the best practices for drug education in elementary classrooms. Teachers can incorporate successful strategies into their teaching methods, creating a more engaging and dynamic learning environment for their learners. Stakeholders. The study's findings informed them of possible as-

sistance to empower teachers with the necessary resources and support to effectively utilize creative methods in drug education. This can include providing professional development opportunities and access to relevant materials and resources. Future Researchers. The results generated from this research provided comprehensive data in conducting future research with similar or relevant scope.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—The basis of this study lay in David Kolb's (1984) experiential learning theory. The relationship between experiential learning theory and creative teaching approaches in drug education was closely intertwined. Experiential Learning Theory emphasizes the significance of learning through direct experiences and active engagement. Creative teaching approaches, which involve hands-on activities, simulations, and real-life scenarios, align perfectly with the principles of experiential learning. Kolb (1984) theorized that individuals learn best when they directly engage with the subject matter through concrete experiences. Creative teaching approaches in drug education provided opportunities for learners to immerse themselves in experiential activities related to drug use, its consequences, and prevention. He added that both experiential learning and creative teaching prioritized active student engagement. So, instead of passively receiving information, learners were actively involved in the learning process, making connections, and drawing conclusions about drugs and apply their knowledge and skills in real-world situations. Furthermore, Kolb (1984) emphasized that experiential learning involves active experimentation and the exploration of different solutions. Therefore, creative teaching approaches encouraged students to experiment with various creative expressions and problem-solving strategies to explore drug-related concepts. This also evoked emotions related to drug use, facil-

itating a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Ultimately, the relationship between experiential learning theory and creative teaching approaches enriches the learning experience and contributes to positive outcomes in drug education. The approach enabled learners to develop a deeper understanding of the complexities of drug-related issues, promoted critical thinking, and empowered them to make informed decisions about drug use and prevention strategies. The alternative approach to drug abuse prevention is based on the concept that individuals provided with healthful, nonchemical ways of gaining rewards and pleasures will be less likely to engage in drug or alcohol abuse. In addition to Experiential Learning Theory, the Cognitive Load Theory, introduced by John Sweller in 1988, elucidated the influence of creative teaching approaches in drug education. Cognitive load theory and creative teaching approaches in drug education revolved around optimizing the learning experience for students. Cognitive load theory emphasizes the importance of managing the cognitive load on learners' working memory. Creative teaching approaches in drug education helped manage the cognitive load by presenting information in visually appealing and interactive ways. These approaches broke down complex drug-related concepts into more manageable and accessible chunks, reducing learners' working memory burden. Moreover, creative teaching approaches often incorporate various media and materials, catering to different learn-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

ing styles and preferences. This multimodal approach reduced cognitive load by offering multiple entry points for students to understand drug education content. Learners engage with the material in ways that best align with their cognitive strengths. By leveraging creative teaching approaches in drug education, teachers optimized the learning process, ensuring that students are actively engaged, motivated, and able to process information effectively. These approaches considered the limitations of cognitive load, providing learners with a balanced and supportive learning environment that facilitates their understanding of drug-related topics. The NDEP (National Drug Education Program) is a comprehensive educational program that provides a holistic approach to the problem of drug abuse. It was designed to enable all sectors to work collaboratively, with the school system as the core, thereby unifying all sectoral endeavors. Responding to these risky behaviors before they

become problematic can be difficult. Furthermore, it is important to understand that risk factors do not, in and of themselves, determine drug use and abuse. Studies of multiple risk factors have found that risk factors have a cumulative effect – i.e., the more risk factors a youth is exposed to, the greater the likelihood that he or she will engage in delinquent or violent behavior (Alberta Alcohol and Drug Abuse Commission,. 2006) The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. Based on the figure, there were three interconnected working themes. These variables were the (1) challenges of teachers in employing creative approaches in drug education for public school teachers, (2) educational insights can be drawn from the experiences of the teachers in employing creative approaches in drug education, and (3) teachers cope with the challenges of employing creative approaches in drug education for elementary school teachers.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presented the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitated the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It established the background for the following conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions had different types and were elaborated below.

Ontology. This part of the research pertained to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2019), reality was subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addressed the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the experiences of teachers in employing creative approaches in drug education for elementary school students were explored. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed.

Epistemology. This referred to the awareness of how knowledge claims were justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (n.d.), as cited by Creswell (2019), stated that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself from the participants. He suggested that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider'. This study intended to gather information from the teachers regarding their experiences in employing creative approaches in drug education for elementary school learners. It was assured that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry.

Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2019) averred that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. The researcher ensured the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understood the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in light of the participants' interpretation.

Rhetoric. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher wrote in a literary, informal style using the personal voice, using qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person to elucidate public elementary school teachers.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method. Methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2019). In this study, teachers' experiences in employing creative approaches in drug education for elementary school students were investigated, particularly those public elementary school teachers of Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of their experiences became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means which is considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena." By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the teachers in a manner that, as David (2019) wrote, the themes, symbols,

and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience is a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge; this experience was a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research was that the everyday world was a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and we could learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2019). By using phenomenology, which concerns the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 2019), the researcher projected that the subjective experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the teachers were explored and insights were drawn as a basis for possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design since it focused on teachers' experiences in employing creative approaches in drug education for elementary school learners. Creswell (2019), asserted that phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes that were grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation,

or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2019) also added that phenomenology, with its roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, attempted to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher used bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. As Corbetta (2020) added, the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provided an in-depth method that granted access to deep knowledge and explanations and helped grasp the subjects' perspectives. Creswell (2019) also claimed that interviews were primarily used in qualitative research. They occurred when researchers asked one or more participants general, open-ended questions and recorded their

answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews were also useful for following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to further investigate their responses. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 2019). Based on Quad's (2019) statements, the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after the interview. Interviews were particularly useful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data, typically via extended interviews, from individuals who had experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, which extracted significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, a textural description of what was experienced, and a structural description of how it was ex-

perienced. The researcher incorporated his or her personal meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult. The researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her personal observations were incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. They were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess teachers' experiences in employing creative approaches in drug education for elementary school students, the researcher intended to use phenomenological methods in qualitative research.

2.4. Research Participants—The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2019). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings were authentic (Marshall, 2019). The participants of this study were the 8 public ele-

mentary school teachers of Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) had been in the present position for at least 5 years- regardless of their age, sex, and marital status; (2) had delivered drug education to elementary school teachers for at least 5 years- regardless of their age, sex, and marital status; and (2) had at least very satisfactory rating in their IPCRF.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—

Ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations were specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needed to adhere to the aims of the research, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. The research was essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was specifically conducted among the teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushed the researcher's interest was teachers' experiences in employing creative approaches in drug education for elementary school students. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2019), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary in nature and was based on the understanding of adequate information. The participant recruitment and selection were lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2019). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating in the research. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of this study were capable of answering the research instrument, for they were all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she could easily be reached through the contact number and be addressed in case there were some clarifications or questions about the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members if they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, if respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were safe during the conduct of the survey and interview. Thus, the distribution of the questionnaire was conducted in a safe venue and administered at their convenient time. The dominant concern of this study is the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were given consideration so that there was no conflict of interest among the researcher and the respon-

dents. Any type of misleading information, as well as representation of primary data findings in a biased way, were avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to give their full honesty in answering the survey questions, and additionally, any type of communication in relation to the research was done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the results of the study. Transparency. The respondents and heads of the participating schools could access the study's results because the information was available and placed on a CD or other storage device, which could be requested from the researcher. In addition, by learning from the study's results, participants were aware of its significance and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each of the participants was advised that they had the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they could be requested and allowed to verify their individual transcript after the interview was carried out. This provided the participants with the opportunity to amend or remove any information which they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and changing names and or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she possessed the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher completed the academic requirements, passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis

writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree, and was qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study reached its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived that the study can be completed successfully in the specified time and that he or she was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped in the enhancement of the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations for the improvement of the study. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed in the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the local traditions, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher necessarily expressed great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said his or her own way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present in working on the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included, or purposefully put forward conclusions that are not accurate.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—I had a responsibility to uncover, transfer, and exploit knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, the researcher took up the

following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. I conducted interviews with the participants and guided them in the process. The researcher in-

terpreted ideas and responded based on existing literature and related studies, not on the researcher's own knowledge, thoughts, and feelings, to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. I implemented the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assessed himself and sought help from the research adviser and other research professionals. These helped him exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews properly according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. I ensured different ways of making a record of what was said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and/or video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher were properly secured as

2.7. *Data Collection*—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. In September 2023, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument explaining the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. The researcher waited for the SDS's response before conducting the study. Asking permission from the School Heads. In the same month, after securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. In September 2023, the re-

they contained sensitive information and were relevant to the research. However, the data were being collected, a primary responsibility of the researcher was to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding were clearly articulated to participants and were approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begun. Analyst of data. I saw the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing, checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher made sure that the findings were true to the participants and that their voices were heard. I organized and presented data. I presented the problem and the related literature and studies that supported it. The study's findings were presented through research questions, stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gave future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

searcher asked permission from the participants. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the Interview. From September to December 2023, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. From January to February 2024, the researcher transcribed the responses of the interviewees precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and Themating. In March 2024, after the transcription, the data

were categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual data within the participants were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell’s Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2019), themes in qualitative research were similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis. The researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis. It involved generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a method of data reduction; it was also an analytic process, so codes captured both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. In the analysis stage, the gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted in accordance with key issues and themes. This involved a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 2020). Famil-

participants. Additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants in order to come up with patterns and trends.

item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each individual theme, and the relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes: The researcher prepared a detailed analysis of each theme identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme. Writing-up involved weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature. The researcher made sure that teachers’ experiences in employing creative approaches in drug education for elementary school students were presented comprehensively.

iarization refers to the process during which the researcher became familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected, such as interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field notes, and gained an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 2020). In other words, the researcher became immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher became aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and made a note of them.

Due to the sheer volume of data that was collected in qualitative research, the researcher was not able to review all the material. Thus, a selection of the data set was utilized. The selection depended on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, the mix of methods used, for example, interviews, documents, and observations. Identifying a thematic framework, the second stage, occurred after familiarization when the researcher recognized emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues had arisen from a priori themes issues. However, it was at this stage that the researcher allowed the data to dictate the themes and issues. To achieve this end, the researcher used the notes taken during the familiarization stage. The key issues, concepts, and themes that had been expressed by the participants now formed the basis of a thematic framework that was used to filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 2020). Indexing meant identifying portions or sections of the data that corresponded to a particular theme. This process was applied to all the textual data that had been

gathered (e.g., transcripts of interviews). For the sake of convenience, Ritchie and Spencer (2019) recommend that a numerical system be used for the indexing references and annotated in the margin beside the text. Qualitative data analysis tools were ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, involved the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis was able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon thus guiding the researcher in his/her interpretation of the data set. It was at this point that the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis, which were: “defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie and Spencer, 2019). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations were reflective of the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echoed the true attitudes, beliefs, and values of the participants.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability were to be relatively foreign to the field of qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substituted data trustworthiness, which consisted of components such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2019). Credibility involved establishing that the findings of the research were credible or believable from the perspectives of the participants. Observing the attributes of prolonged engagement is where credibility contributed to a belief in the trustworthiness of data. To address the issue of credibility, the researcher interviewed as many research participants as possible or up to the

point of saturation. Meanwhile, transferability was the degree to which the findings were generalized or transferred to other contexts. In this, the researcher did a thorough job in describing the research context and assumptions that were relevant. On the other hand, dependability was the consistency and repeatability of the research. The researcher made sure that the study’s findings were evaluated by the participants and scrutinized by an external reviewer. Lastly, conformability was the degree to which findings could be confirmed or corroborated by other researchers. The researcher documented the procedures and rechecked the data during the entire research process. The researcher also made sure that the findings were true and correct.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents and discusses the study's results with reference to its aim. Moreover, it discusses the themes that emerged from the data gathered. The results present the description and background of the participants who were assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities.

3.1. Challenges of Teachers in Employing Creative Approaches in Drug Education for Public School Teachers—Teachers in public elementary schools face various situations while employing creative teaching approaches in drug education, encountering challenges and positive outcomes. Their responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on what came from informants' accounts and reflections.

3.1.1. Challenges Encountered: Superficial Understanding—While creative teaching approaches that introduce highly entertaining activities can captivate learners in the immediate moment, they may not necessarily foster a profound and comprehensive understanding of issues related to drugs. Learners might prioritize the enjoyment derived from the activities rather than grasping the substantive content of the lesson. The participant expressed concern that creative teaching approaches, if not carefully balanced, may have the unintended consequences of becoming distracting for the learners. Learners may divert their attention away from the core educational content as they become engrossed in the fun elements. This distraction can lead to a limited understanding of the subject matter. Learners may struggle to apply critical skills if they have only a limited understanding of the lesson. This negative experience of the participant in employing creative teaching approaches in drug education is supported by several researchers. Midford and McBride (2019) argued that an overemphasis on the fun element results in a superficial understanding of drug-related issues. Students were more inclined to enjoy the entertaining aspects of the lesson rather than delving deeply into the complexities and implications of drug education. Also, the substance of the content is overshadowed by the entertaining elements, leading to a dilution of educational depth and this impairs learners' retention of information and their ability to apply knowledge in real-world scenarios. Moreover, Silvia et al. (2019) found out that an overemphasis on fun leads to a decrease in motivation for serious learning. Learners approach academic tasks with the expectation of entertainment, potentially affecting their engagement with more rigorous or challenging content. While Shope et al. (2019) found out that an overemphasis on fun in early educational experiences create challenges when learners need to transition to more serious or formal academic contexts. They also pointed out that, if the emphasis is consistently on enjoyment rather than academic rigor, learners develop habits that prioritize entertainment over productive study strategies.

3.1.2. Potential Misinterpretation—Creative teaching methods elicit subjective interpretations, allowing learners to articulate their thoughts and emotions through a variety of means. This diversity in expression can result in differing understandings of the subject matter. The participants expressed reservations about the efficacy of creative teaching approaches, citing concerns that the non-traditional methods might hinder rather than enhance student under-

standing of the material. According to their perspective, non-traditional teaching approaches might not reliably foster the thorough comprehension typically attained in a standard learning environment. This is linked to the unique delivery style, incorporating entertainment and aesthetics into the intended instructional material. This unification has the potential to confuse students as the precise learning goals are overshadowed. For example, in activities such as poster making and role playing, students are prompted to actively interpret the core of the lesson, occasionally diverting attention from the crucial factual components of the subject matter. The participants' negative experience aligned with findings from various researchers. Stead (2019) suggested creative teaching methods emphasizing varied interpretations may introduce

3.1.3. Positive Effects: Increased Learner Self-confidence—Utilizing creative teaching methods enables learners to articulate their thoughts, emotions, and viewpoints on matters related to drugs through a range of art-oriented activities. As students witness the appreciation and respect for their ideas, they develop confidence in their capacity to communicate and contribute meaningfully. For the participants, it is remarkable how creative teaching approaches have broken down the barriers of shyness among students when it comes to discussing drugs. The interactive and expressive nature of these methods has opened up a space where learners feel comfortable tackling this sensitive topic. Moreover, the participants also revealed that through the integration of creative approaches in drug education, learners now embrace the opportunity to also engage creatively, fostering a more inclusive and confident learning environment. Certain researchers substantiate this positive experience of the participants. Researchers have explored the influence of creative teaching approaches on learners' confidence in the context of drug education. Several

ambiguity in learning outcomes. When students are encouraged to interpret lesson material in diverse ways, it might be challenging for teachers to ensure that core learning objectives are consistently met. Additionally, Maggs and Schulenberg (2020) discovered that allowing too much flexibility in interpretation may lead to miscommunication of key concepts. If students interpret lesson material in ways significantly different from the intended meaning, it may result in misunderstandings and gaps in their understanding of fundamental concepts. Dijkstra et al. (2019) also argued that encouraging varied interpretations without sufficient guidance may result in learners lacking a common knowledge base. This lack of shared understanding could hinder collaborative learning and discussions within the classroom.

studies suggest that integrating creative methods, such as art-based activities, role-playing, and interactive discussions, can have a positive impact on learners' confidence levels. For instance, Toumbourou and Gregg (2020), discussed that creative approaches stimulate critical thinking skills. By encouraging learners to think critically about drug-related issues and express their opinions, these methods contribute to the development of confidence in their ability to analyze and articulate their thoughts. Also, White and Pitts (2019) found out that creative approaches stimulate critical thinking skills. By encouraging learners to think critically about drug-related issues and express their opinions, these methods contribute to the development of confidence in their ability to analyze and articulate their thoughts. For Rehm (2019), drug education should be made personally relevant to learners' life. Creative approaches allow teachers to tailor lessons to the specific interests and experiences of learners, making the material more relatable. The positive impact of creative teaching approaches on students' life may extend beyond the immediate classroom setting.

Learners who develop confidence in discussing drug education topics creatively may be more likely to continue engaging with these issues outside of the classroom.

3.1.4. Improved Learner Presentation and Communication Skills—Creative teaching approaches provide changes for learners to showcase their projects or express their ideas about drugs in a public classroom setting. The participant also held the belief that learners could potentially assume roles or professions in the future focused on eliminating drugs and drug addiction in society. This implies that they might actively contribute to guiding the youth away from drugs if teachers inspire them to have zero tolerance for drugs and cultivate their communication skills, enabling them to encourage young individuals to become responsible citizens. Research exploring the effects of creative teaching approaches on learners' presentation and communication further supports the positive experiences reported by the participants. Midford and McBride (2018) asserted that incorporating creative approaches in teaching enhances learners' communication skills. The engagement in diverse activities, such as role-playing, discussions, and creative projects, stimulates effective verbal and non-verbal communication. Meanwhile, Gorman (2018) highlighted the link between active participation in creative activities and improved communication skills. . When learners are encouraged to express themselves creatively, it not only deepens their understanding but also fosters better articulation of ideas

in both written and spoken forms. Furthermore, Bruvold (2018) suggested that the communication and presentation skills honed through creative teaching approaches are transferable and contribute to learners' success in future professional endeavors. Also, the adaptability cultivated through creative teaching methods translates into a valuable skill set for learners navigating dynamic work environments, where effective communication and presentation are essential. The figure 3 shows the emerging themes regarding teachers' challenges in employing creative approaches in drug education for public school teachers. The positive effects of these challenges are also depicted in the diagram. The emerging themes regarding teachers' challenges were superficial understanding and potential misinterpretation. Meanwhile, the positive effects of the challenges are increased student self-confidence and improved learner communication and presentation skills. The themes suggest that teachers have positive encounters related to creative teaching approaches, wherein they prioritize interactive and engaging activities in the classroom. However, there is a potential downside to this approach, as it may accentuate the risks of incomplete comprehension of the material and challenges in the learning process if not employed judiciously or with expertise by teachers.

3.2. Coping Strategies of Public Elementary School Teachers in Creative Approaches in Drug Education—Teachers have different ways to address their challenges in employing cre-

ative approaches in drug education. Their responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on what came from informants' accounts and reflections.

3.2.1. Designing Purposeful Activity Design—

Fig. 3. Challenges of Teachers in Employing Creative Approaches in Drug Education for Public School Teachers

Teachers craft purposeful creative activities, ensuring that each enjoyable element serves an educational objective and reinforces key concepts in drug education. Additionally, they develop well-rounded lesson plans that integrate both enjoyable and educational components, aiming to achieve a balance between engagement and learning. This approach ensures learners' active involvement in the educational process. The participants implied that purposeful activities are the heart of creative teaching in drug education. They allow students to actively participate, turning passive learners into engaged contributors. It's not just about what they know but how they apply that knowledge in their lives. Purposeful activities also enable learners to apply their knowledge and critical thinking skills in situations they may encounter outside these walls. These kinds of activities have positive impact on learners' learning in drug education. The participants further explained that activities that connect to real-life situations in drug education have a ripple effect on students' learning. It transforms the learning experience from theoretical to practical, empowering learners to apply their knowledge and make informed choices in real-world contexts. In addition, the participants also emphasized perceiving the content as relevant and applica-

ble to their lives serves as a powerful motivator, maintaining their engagement even when there are fun or entertaining elements. The connection to real-world situations captures their attention and helps them see the practical importance of the educational content. The coping strategy employed by the participants is supported by various researchers. Foxcroft et al. (2020) asserted that creating connections between lessons and real-life situations fosters a learner-centered learning environment, encouraging active learner participation by demonstrating the direct application of their studies to potential real-world scenarios. This engagement ensures that the educational content remains at the forefront, even when enjoyable elements are incorporated. Furthermore, Nilsen (2019) elucidated that lessons linked to real-life scenarios contribute to improved retention and recall of information. The ability of students to anchor new knowledge to practical experiences creates enduring memory associations. Lastly, Midford (2021) highlighted that purposefully designing learning activities motivates students to explore topics in-depth when they recognize the practical implications of the lesson, encouraging a more thorough understanding of the subject matter.

3.2.2. Clearing Learning Objectives—The participants emphasized that the creative activities are in sync with the overarching learning objectives of the drug education curriculum. This alignment helps provide clarity to both teachers and learners regarding what specific knowledge, skills, and attitudes the activities are intended to reinforce, not the entertainment or aesthetics element of the lesson. The responses showcased how clear learning objectives, when integrated with creative teaching approaches, contribute to a more comprehensive and engaging understanding of drug education

for learners. Knowing the learning objectives motivates learners to actively engage with the material. Creative teaching approaches leverage this motivation by making the learning process dynamic and participatory. Interactive activities, role plays, or multimedia presentations become tools that students willingly embrace to achieve the stated objectives. The responses of the participants regarding having a clear learning objective when employing creative teaching approaches were connected to the findings of several researchers. For instance, Faggiano et al. (2021) highlighted the need for clear learning

objectives to strike a balance between enjoyment and educational goals. When objectives are well-defined, creative teaching approaches can incorporate enjoyable elements while staying focused on achieving specific educational outcomes. Darcy (2018) also emphasized that clear learning objectives strike a balance between enjoyment and educational goals. When objectives are well-defined, creative teaching approaches can incorporate enjoyable elements while staying focused on achieving specific ed-

3.2.3. Personalizing Learning—Teachers tailor learners’ learning experiences to accommodate the varied learning needs and levels of the students. Creative activities are adjusted to align with the abilities and resources of each learners. The participants acknowledged that learners may progress at different paces. When incorporating creative approaches, teachers can allow learners to move through content at a speed that suits their understanding, ensuring that each student has the time and support needed for mastery. Learners have different learning styles—some are visual learners, while others may learn best through hands-on experiences or discussions. Creative approaches, such as role playing, poster making, or technology integration, allow teachers to cater to varied learning styles, ensuring that each learner can engage with the material in a way that suits them best. This coping way of the participants has a positive effect on the learning outcomes of learners in drug education. The responses of the participants showed that creative teaching fosters a continuous feedback loop. Through

3.2.4. Aligning with Evidence-based Information—Teachers derive the content of creative activities from evidence-based information and credible sources. They ensure the information presented during creative tasks aligns with the

educational outcomes. When students know the specific outcomes, they are working toward, it helps them concentrate on acquiring the necessary knowledge and skills. Overall, research indicates a positive correlation between clear learning objectives and improved student performance. When learners have a clear understanding of what is expected, they are more likely to perform well in assessments and demonstrate mastery of the material.

interactive projects and discussions, they gain insights into their learners’ understanding. This allows for timely adjustments and targeted support, contributing to improved performance on assessments. The findings of Cooper (2018) demonstrated a positive correlation between creative teaching and student motivation. When learners find the learning experience enjoyable and personally meaningful, their motivation increases, contributing to sustained effort and ultimately higher scores in assessments. Likewise, Burke (2021) noted that providing students with choices in how they demonstrate their understanding positively impacts their empowerment and motivation. This autonomy in creative projects correlates with increased effort and better scores in subsequent assessments. Furthermore, Almeida, et al. (2022) stressed that establishing strong teacher- learner relationships is foundational for personalized learning in drug education. By building trust, teachers can create an environment where learners feel comfortable discussing sensitive topics, enabling a more personalized and impactful educational experience.

drug education curriculum and accurate data. They rely on reputable sources of information such as scientific journals, government health agencies, and reputable educational organizations for drug-related facts and data. The partic-

Participants emphasized that aligning with evidence-based information fosters independence and enhances critical thinking skills in learners, enabling them to interpret lessons autonomously, even when the content incorporates elements of entertainment and aesthetics. Exposure to evidence-based drug education can have a lasting impact on behavior. Students may carry their understanding of drug-related issues into adulthood, influencing choices related to substance use. The coping strategy adopted by the participants finds support in various research findings. Studies such as those conducted by Bosworth and Sloboda (2020) underscore the efficacy of teaching with evidence-based information in establishing a robust foundation for critical thinking. This method encourages students to scrutinize information, distinguish between facts and opinions, validate their experiences, and cultivate analytical skills essential for navigating a complex world. The research also emphasizes that this approach is instrumental in nurturing lifelong learners. Prioritizing critical thinking equips learners to navigate a world saturated with misinformation, fostering a mindset that actively seeks truth and verifiable knowledge. Additionally, Cahill (2023) highlights that aligning with evidence-based

information diminishes the likelihood of misinterpreting content. Learners with a better grasp of accurate information are less prone to errors in assessments. The figure 4 shows the emerging themes on the coping strategies of public elementary school teachers for the challenges of employing creative approaches in drug education. The themes were designing purposeful activity design, clearing learning objectives, personalizing learning, and aligning with evidence-based information. The interplay of these research themes forms a holistic approach to teachers' coping strategies. Designing purposeful activities ensures that creativity is purposefully directed toward educational goals. Clearing learning objectives provides a roadmap for both teachers and learners, preventing the potential pitfalls of misinterpretation. Personalizing learning addresses the diverse needs of students, making creative approaches more accessible and effective. Aligning with evidence-based information adds a layer of credibility, ensuring that creativity does not compromise the accuracy and reliability of the educational content. Together, these themes contribute to a comprehensive coping strategy for teachers facing challenges in implementing creative approaches in drug education.

3.3. Educational Insights Drawn from the Experiences of Public Elementary School Teachers—The insights derived from the experiences of participants in the realm of employing creative teaching approaches in drug education offer valuable perspectives that contribute sig-

nificantly to the enhancement of teaching and learning practices in drug education. The participants' responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on what came from informants' accounts and reflections.

3.3.1. Responsible Decision-Making—In drug education, the participant's goal is to be more than just a source of information – they want to be a catalyst for responsible decision-making. By incorporating creative teaching ap-

proaches, they strike a balance between engaging, enjoyable lessons and the delivery of crucial academic content. The participants implied that finding the delicate balance in teaching not only ensures learners absorb vital information

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on the Coping Strategies of Public Elementary School Teachers for the Challenges of Employing Creative Approaches in Drug Education

but also actively engages them in their learning journey. It is about creating an environment where knowledge is not just received but experienced, fostering a deeper understanding and a lasting impact on their education. Responsible decision-making by teachers is the cornerstone of achieving a delicate balance in teaching, particularly in maintaining equilibrium between content delivery and student engagement. It involves thoughtful and intentional choices in selecting instructional methods, designing curriculum, and fostering a classroom atmosphere that is both informative and captivating. When teachers make responsible decisions, they prioritize not only the dissemination of essential content but also the creation of an environment where students are actively engaged in the learning process. The participant emphasized that students' path to success involves being responsible decision-makers. This means knowing when to indulge in the lesson's enjoyment and when to channel their focus into absorbing the intended learning. It's a skill that molds them into effective learners. Several researchers have supported the reflection of participants on the multifaceted role of teachers in promoting responsible decision-making. According to Halpern-Felsher (2019), teachers play a diverse role, and the incorporation

of creative teaching approaches is consistently highlighted as a nuanced method for skillfully blending academic content with engaging methods. Similarly, Goldberg (2022) emphasizes the importance of teachers adopting a balanced approach that not only captures students' interest through enjoyable elements but also ensures the substantive delivery of educational content. This equilibrium is acknowledged as crucial for establishing a conducive and effective learning environment. Furthermore, the advocacy for responsible decision-making extends to motivating students to take responsibility for their decisions. Doubeni et al. (2020) explore the concept that students should actively embrace the role of responsible decision-makers. There is a recognized imperative for learners to master the art of balancing their focus and priorities in the classroom. Researchers argue against a one-sided pursuit of enjoyment, emphasizing that learners should approach lessons critically, engaging with the material with the intent of thoroughly learning the designated content. A focus solely on entertainment may lead to students struggling to comprehend and retain essential academic content, resulting in lower academic performance and a lack of mastery in the subject matter.

3.3.2. Proficiency in Connecting Ideas— Proficiency in linking ideas is a crucial competency for learners, particularly when exposed to creative teaching approaches. The participants implied that students should be able to discern the relationship between different concepts, leading to a clearer and more comprehensive understanding of the lesson. Mastery in connecting ideas helps students create a coherent mental framework, allowing them to organize information logically and make sense of the content presented in creative ways. The reflections shared by the participants align with Coggans'

(2021) assertion that proficiency in connecting diverse concepts plays a crucial role in supporting deep learning. When learners can establish relationships between different ideas, they are more likely to participate in meaningful learning experiences that transcend surface-level understanding. Additionally, the findings suggest that connecting diverse concepts facilitates the transferability of knowledge, enabling learners to apply their learning to novel contexts and demonstrating the practical utility of their acquired knowledge. Butters (2021) further emphasizes that connecting diverse concepts is intricately

linked to the enhancement of critical thinking skills, encouraging learners to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information, thereby fostering a more sophisticated approach to problem-solving and decision-making. Furthermore, as noted by Coombes et al. (2019), the ability to

connect diverse concepts enhances metacognitive awareness. Learners become more aware of their thinking processes, allowing them to reflect on how different ideas interrelate and contribute to their overall understanding.

3.3.3. Expression of Individuality—The participants understood that creative teaching encourages learners to express their ideas and perspectives in unique ways. This freedom of expression allows them to showcase talents that might not be apparent in more rigid instructional settings. Participants believed that by taking these actions, teachers not only support the development of learners' talents but also create a dynamic and enriching learning environment that values and celebrates the diversity of skills within the classroom. These reflections align with the findings of Cuijpers (2022), highlighting that creative teaching approaches facilitate personalized learning experiences, enabling students to explore and articulate their distinct perspectives and talents within the educational context. These methods are also conducive to recognizing diverse learning styles, fostering a growth mindset that views challenges as opportunities to uncover optimal learning approaches. This heightened awareness empowers teachers to customize instruction according to individual

preferences, enhancing the overall learning journey. Additionally, Ellickson (2018) observed that creative teaching serves as a catalyst for self-discovery, providing students with innovative avenues to delve into their interests and identify their unique talents, strengths, and areas for growth. The figure 5 shows the emerging themes of educational management insights drawn from the teachers' experiences in employing creative approaches in drug education. The themes were responsible decision-making, proficiency in connecting ideas, and expression of individuality. Incorporating these interrelated themes into creative teaching approaches ensures a more holistic and effective drug education program. It not only equips learners with factual knowledge but also develops their critical thinking skills, empathy, and a sense of personal responsibility. Ultimately, this interconnected approach empowers students to make informed decisions about drug use while fostering a culture of understanding and open communication.

4. Implications and Future Directions

Presented in this chapter was a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on the findings of the study. Future directions in the field of experiences of teachers were also discussed here.

4.1. Findings—The study provided a detailed examination of how public elementary school teachers address drug education using creative methods. It offered valuable insights into teachers' challenges and coping strategies, contributing to the field of educational manage-

ment. The study presented a mixed picture, highlighting both the challenges and the positive effects experienced by teachers using creative methods in drug education. Several participants reported increased self-confidence and better communication skills. However, there

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on Educational Insights Drawn from the Experiences of the Public Elementary School Teachers in Employing Creative Approaches in Drug Education

were also concerns about superficial learning and potential misinterpretation of the content. Teachers dealt with these challenges effectively through their creative leadership. They targeted function-driven goal creation, design regarding learning objectives, personalized learning, and intake of evidence-based data to upgrade learners' learning results. Furthermore, insights from public school elementary teachers emphasized the enhancement of learner responsibility, connecting ideas to deepen understanding, and fostering individuality. This provides educational managers with a foundation to support teachers

4.2. Implications—The study investigated the experiences of public elementary school teachers in employing creative approaches in drug education. The emerging themes on the experiences of teachers in employing creative approaches in drug education were divided into positive and negative experiences. On positive experiences, the themes were increased student self-confidence and improved learner communication and presentation skills. On negative experiences, the themes were superficial learning and potential misinterpretation. An implication of these research findings is the importance of public elementary school teachers using positive experiences and dealing with negative ones when teaching drug education creatively to learners. By recognizing both the good and bad parts of using creative methods in drug education, public elementary school teachers can improve their teaching to help learners learn better and have a more enjoyable learning experience. Furthermore, the emerging themes on how public elementary school teachers cope

4.3. Future Directions—Data obtained had implications for various stakeholders in education including policymakers, school administrators, and teachers. The future directions for

in implementing more creative methods, making teaching more engaging for learners. By fostering a supportive environment and aiding in the creation of teaching materials and a drug education curriculum, education managers empower public school elementary teachers to excel in delivering high-quality drug education. Through effective management, schools can ensure that learners develop the knowledge, skills, confidence, and resilience needed to make informed decisions and navigate challenges in today's complex world.

with challenges in using creative approaches for drug education were designing purposeful activities, clearing learning objectives, personalizing learning, and aligning with evidence-based information. This research findings suggest that public elementary school teachers should have effective coping mechanisms to overcome challenges in implementing creative approaches for drug education. It underscores the importance of enhancing the efficacy of their teaching methods and better-engaging learners in drug education. Lastly, the emerging themes in the educational insights drawn from the experiences of public elementary school teachers were promoting responsible decision-making, proficiency in connecting ideas, and expression of individuality. These research findings suggest that public elementary school teachers were significant in fostering a holistic approach to drug education. This was essential for the development of a comprehensive drug education curriculum where learners were empowered and engaged in their learning experiences.

this study that could play a role in influencing the trajectory of employing creative teaching approaches in drug education were as follows: Policymakers may explore the development and im-

plementation of specialized teacher training programs that focus on equipping teachers with the skills and knowledge needed to effectively incorporate creative teaching approaches in drug education. They could assess the outcomes and effectiveness of such training initiatives. Moreover, they could help explore strategies to align creative teaching approaches with established curriculum standards in drug education. They could facilitate the seamless integration of creative methods into standardized curriculum requirements to ensure a cohesive educational experience. Meanwhile, school principals may investigate the development of systematic observation and feedback systems for teachers to assess the implementation of creative teaching approaches in drug education. They could explore how feedback mechanisms can support teachers in refining their methods and addressing potential challenges. Moreover, they could also assess the impact of involving stakeholders in shaping a positive perception of these methods and fostering community support for teachers. In addition, public elementary school teachers may explore the potential benefits of interdisciplinary collaboration among teachers in different subjects within a school. Examine how collaborative efforts can enrich the integration of creative teaching approaches in drug education, providing a holistic educational experience. They may also go research about global perspectives on creative teaching approaches in drug education. Explore best practices from different educational contexts, identifying innovative methods that can be adapted and implemented effectively by teachers. Lastly, future researchers may engage in the development of similar or different contexts of this study. They may examine the intersection of creative teaching approaches and culturally responsive teaching in the context of drug education. They may also explore how public elementary school teachers tailor creative methods to resonate with diverse cultural backgrounds and promote inclusivity. Moreover, they may also investigate robust assessment strategies to help these teachers measure both the creative and academic achievements of learners when creative teaching approaches were employed in drug education. These future directions serve as a guide in exploring new avenues, refining existing practices, and advancing the field of creative teaching in drug education. By addressing these future directions, public elementary school teachers can continuously enhance their pedagogical approaches, contributing to a dynamic and effective learning environment for learners.

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